

RESEARCH PAPER

ORGANOLEPTIC ASSESSMENT OF STORED PROCESSED GIANT AFRICAN SNAIL MEAT PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the organoleptic assessment of the giant African Land Snail meat products. Four different treatments were considered for evaluation in this study; unseasoned fried (USF), seasoned fried (SF), seasoned oven- dried (SOD) and seasoned smoke- dried (SSD). The products were kept under three storage conditions (ambient, refrigeration and freezer temperature). The results showed that the mean score of unseasoned fried product (3.950) and seasoned oven-dried products (3.800) had declined in colour quality at 20days freezer storage. Besides, freezer stored meat products were better shelf stable. The result showed that seasoned smoke-dried product under freezer storage was ranked the highest score (5.000) at 30 days in taste. Seasoned smoke-dried product under freezer storage was ranked the highest score (5.000) at 30 days in terms of juiciness. The tenderness of the different refrigerated products increased with increasing storage periods (10-20 days). This implies that there was gradual increase of moisture in the refrigerated products. Seasoned oven-dried product was the least preferred (2.950) for room storage which lasted for 5days. A similar trend was also observed at 5days storage for all products at room condition. Before day 10 all the products under room storage were terminated based on obvious spoilage. However, products under room temperature could only last for 6days, refrigerated sample 20days while freezer stored products could last beyond 30 days. Snail meat should be processed cured and smoke- dried in order to significantly improve consumption of snail meat products in Nigeria.

KEY WORDS: Snail, cure, organoleptic, taste panel.

Received for Publication: 28/07/15

Accepted for Publication: 10/10/15

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INTRODUCTION

Snails have a long standing importance as a source of human food and products from snail belong to foodstuff with high nutritional value (Tremlova, 2001), containing food energy, high quality proteins, vitamins and minerals. Although, most snails are consumed near or at the place of origin/capture, there is considerable international trade in snail meat as there is also a considerable demand for snail meat. This suggests that most often, snails are transported from their places of origin/capture to urban cities or other countries either alive or in semi-processed form or ready to- eat conditions (ZASBDC, 2008).

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Many species of edible land snails exist but the popular species of economic importance are the West African giant snails: *Archachatina marginata*, *Achatina fulica* and *Achatina achatina*. Snail meat popularly known as “Congo meat” is consumed in Nigeria and many countries in the world. They are used as food and source of income in Nigeria. Edible land snails are abundant during the wet season, when they are easily gathered at night and before dawn. (Ebenso 2002; Ebenso and Okafor 2002; Ebenso 2003) and production is on commercial scale in Nigeria. Snail is very important source of animal protein to man., snails are expensive during the dry season when its price increases and affordability is beyond the reach of average people. Moreover, most people find the processing of snail time consuming and tiresome, especially de-shelling and washing to remove the slime; thereby discouraging interested consumers.

It is also believed that the palatability of the meat and the interest to eat the meat depend on its quality and the processing method employed. Meat quality may be influenced by multiple factors before and after slaughter (Olsson & Pickova, 2005) and depend on diets (Leikus and Norviliene, 2006; Koopmans *et al.*, 2006), feed supplements (Peeters *et al.*, 2006; Niculita *et al.*, 2007), conditions of meat storage (Jukna *et al.*, 2006) etc. Hence, the objective of this study was to carry out organoleptic assessment of the stored processed giant African snail meat products at room, refrigerated and freezer storage with the view to determining the shelf life.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Source of Snails:

A total of 150 adult snails (*Archachatina marginata*) with mean live weight of 346.85g, were collected from Ekiuwa market in Edo State. They were transferred to University of Benin where they were killed.

Preparation of Snail

Snails were fasted for 24 hours in order to empty the gut and to reduce contamination during killing. Then the snails were weighed, killed and separated into meat, shell, waste and fluid. The meats were washed with alum to remove the slime and cut to uniform weight range of 50-55g.

Application of cure:

In this study, snails were cured in a prepared pickle solution containing 1.5% salt, 1.5% sugar, 0.5% thyme, 0.30% nutmeg, 0.30% ginger, 1.50% red pepper, 0.05% sodium sorbate, 0.05% sodium tripolyphosphate, 0.50% curry, 1.50% onion as shown in Table 1 for 24hours in refrigeration temperature, before processing snails by frying, smoke-drying and oven-drying. However, the control was devoid of spices before frying.

Table 1: Pickle Formulation

Ingredients	Percentage (%)	Weight (g)
Sugar	1.50	45
Salt	1.50	45
Tyenne	0.50	15
Nutmeg	0.30	9
Ginger	0.30	9
Redpepper	1.50	45
Sodiun sorbate	0.05	1.5
Sodiun tripolyphosphate	0.05	1.5
Curry	0.5	15
Onion	1.50	45
Water	91.85	2755.5
Total	100%	3000g

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Processing Methods

Smoke-drying

Pickle cured snail meat were skewered with sticks and smoke-dried at 80°C for 2 hours 15 minutes in a smoking kiln at Kilishi factory, Ekenwan campus. Each snail meat was spread out with stick in a traditional bush meat processing manner to increase the surface area of the meat exposed to smoke and heat. The meat samples were spread on racks in the smoking kiln to ensure uniform smoking and drying of the individual product.

Frying

Pickle cured snails were fried at 170°C for 30 minutes in a deep pan fryer with Soya oil.

Oven-drying

Pickle cured snail meats were oven-dried at 90°C (by setting the temperature regulator attached to the oven to 90°C) for 4 hour 30 min using electric oven.

Packaging:

Snail meat products were allowed to cool, the products were packaged one per cellophane for all the products except seasoned smoked product that was skewered and sealed in low density cellophanes with the use of sealing machine.

Plate 1: Packaged snail meat products

Storage Temperatures:

Three storage temperatures were used.

- Room temperature (28.5°C)
- Refrigeration temperature (9.5°C)
- Freezer temperature (-12.5°C)

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Storage Period

Snail meat products were stored for total duration of 30 days and meat samples were withdrawn for analyses as follows.

- 0 day (control)
- 5 days
- 10 days
- 15 days
- 20 days
- 25 days
- 30 days

Sensory Evaluation

Meat samples were served to trained panelists who evaluated the products based on 5- point Hedonic scale. Samples were coded as 311 (unseasoned fried), 312 (seasoned fried), 412 (seasoned oven-dried) and 512 (seasoned smoke-dried). Colour, tenderness, taste, juiciness and overall acceptability of the products were scored by the panelists. The 5- point hedonic scale used to describe the score of attributes of the processed snail meat products include: 5=like extremely, 4=like moderately, 3=neither like nor dislike 2=dislike moderately, 1=dislike extremely.

Data Analysis

Data generated were subjected to analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to test significant variations ($P < 0.05$) among mean values obtained. Where significant differences existed, Duncan's least significance difference test was applied to indicate where the differences occurred using Genstat statistical package 2005, 8TH edition (Genstat Procedure Library Release PL16).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Colour

Colour is one of the most important attributes by which consumers judge the quality of meat and therefore colour deterioration is one of the main factors that limits storage life, at least until the point of purchase. The colour of meat products has significant impact on meat consumers' choice. One of the major response variables governing food acceptance is colour.

Analysis of variance showed that there was significant difference ($P < 0.001$) in the sensory attribute (colour) of the different snail meat products based on treatment applied (Processing methods, storage condition and storage days).

The colour changes due to the interaction between processing methods, storage conditions and storage days are shown in Table 2. Unseasoned fried product (3.950) and seasoned oven-dried products (3.800) declined in colour quality at 20days freezer storage. There was no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) between seasoned fried product and seasoned smoke-dried product under freezer condition throughout the period of storage. Besides, freezer stored snail meat product was better shelf stable. This implies that seasonings and freezer storage prolong and maintain colour quality of meat products. Apata *et al.* (2012) reported that cold storage of meat and meat products prolongs and maintains their quality over reasonable period of time.

Table 2 Mean Values of Colour of Snail Meat Products (Processing methods, storage days and storage conditions).

Products	Storage conditions	Storage period(days)						
		0	5	10	15	20	25	30
311	Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	4.150 ^{abc}	4.500 ^a	4.300 ^{abcde}	4.650 ^a	3.950 ^{efg}	4.200 ^c	4.100 ^c
312	Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	4.250 ^{ab}	4.350 ^a	4.500 ^{ab}	4.450 ^{ab}	4.500 ^{ab}	4.500 ^{ab}	4.900 ^a
412	Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	3.450 ^e	3.656 ^{cde}	4.050 ^{cdefg}	4.200 ^{bcdef}	3.800 ^{gh}	4.000 ^c	4.000 ^c
512	Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	4.050 ^{abcd}	4.400 ^a	4.550 ^{ab}	4.600 ^a	4.600 ^a	4.800 ^a	4.950 ^a
311	Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	4.150 ^{abc}	4.250 ^{ab}	4.00 ^{bcdef}	4.500 ^{ab}	2.850 ^j	-	-
312	Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	4.250 ^{ab}	4.150 ^{abc}	4.350 ^{abcd}	4.000 ^{defg}	3.850 ^{fgh}	-	-
412	Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	3.450 ^e	4.000 ^{abcd}	4.050 ^{cdefg}	3.900 ^{fgh}	3.600 ⁱ	-	-
512	Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	4.050 ^{abcd}	4.300 ^a	4.400 ^{abc}	3.700 ^{gh}	4.200 ^{bcdef}	-	-
311	Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	4.150 ^{abc}	3.550 ^{de}	-	-	-	-	-
312	Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	4.250 ^{ab}	3.700 ^{bcde}	-	-	-	-	-
412	Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	3.450 ^e	3.700 ^{bcde}	-	-	-	-	-
512	Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	4.050 ^{abcd}	3.650 ^{cde}	-	-	-	-	-
SEM		0.1670			0.1101		0.0784	

Means within storage day bracket having same superscript along the row and down the column are not significantly different (P>0.05).

311= unseasoned fried, 312=seasoned fried, 412=seasoned oven-dried, 512=seasoned smoke-dried

Plate 2: Unseasoned fried snail meat product.

Plate 3: Seasoned fried snail meat product.

Plate 4: Seasoned oven-dried snail meat product

Plate 5: Smoke-dried snail meat product

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Taste

It is well known fact that the standard of judging meat product quality is the perfect combination of colour, and taste. Hence, aroma and taste have important impact on meat processing. Although, both of these factors affect the overall acceptability of foods, the flavour volatiles are of utmost importance because they influence the judgment of the consumer even before the food is eaten.

The analysis of variance showed that there was significant difference ($P < 0.001$) in taste of products based on treatment applied (processing methods, storage conditions and storage days).

The interaction between processing methods, storage conditions and storage days of product's taste are shown in Table 3. The result showed that seasoned smoke-dried product under freezer storage was ranked the highest score (5.000) at 30 days. The presence of certain phenolic compounds such as guaiacol and syringol in smoke play an important role in the characteristic flavour of smoked product, smoke components impact and stabilize taste of meat products (Arvanitoyannis and Kotsanopoulos, 2011). Engman *et al.* (2012) reported that smoke generally tends to enhance the flavour of food.

Table 3: Taste: Mean Values of Snail Meat Products (Processing methods, storage days and storage conditions).

		Storage period(days)						
Products	Storage Conditions	0	5	10	15	20	25	30
311	Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	3.950 ^{bc}	4.100 ^b	4.200 ^{def}	3.850 ^{fg}	3.800 ^{ghi}	3.750 ^d	4.250 ^c
312	Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	4.650 ^a	4.150 ^{ab}	4.350 ^{cde}	4.350 ^{cde}	4.450 ^{abcd}	4.450 ^{bc}	4.650 ^b
412	Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	3.200 ^{defg}	3.550 ^{cd}	3.350 ^j	3.500 ^{ghij}	3.950 ^{fg}	3.700 ^d	3.800 ^d
512	Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	4.350 ^{ab}	4.200 ^{ab}	4.850 ^{ab}	4.650 ^{abc}	4.450 ^{abcd}	4.600 ^b	5.000 ^a
311	Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	3.950 ^{bc}	4.200 ^{ab}	4.150 ^{def}	3.350 ^{ij}	2.350 ^k	-	-
312	Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	4.650 ^a	4.200 ^{ab}	4.200 ^{def}	4.050 ^{def}	3.550 ^{ghij}	-	-
412	Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	3.200 ^{defg}	3.500 ^{cde}	3.450 ^{hij}	3.400 ^{ij}	2.650 ^k	-	-
512	Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	4.350 ^{ab}	4.000 ^{bc}	4.850 ^a	3.950 ^{fg}	4.400 ^{cd}	-	-
311	Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	3.950 ^{bc}	3.300 ^{def}	-	-	-	-	-
312	Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	4.650 ^a	3.000 ^{efg}	-	-	-	-	-
412	Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	3.200 ^{defg}	2.900 ^{fg}	-	-	-	-	-
512	Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	4.350 ^{ab}	2.750 ^g	-	-	-	-	-
SEM		0.1636		0.1347		0.1484		

Means within storage day bracket having same superscript along the row and down the column are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$).

311= unseasoned fried, 312=seasoned fried, 412=seasoned oven-dried, 512=seasoned smoke-dried

Juiciness

Meat juiciness is an important factor of meat tenderness and palatability and it has two major components- the first is the impression of wetness produced by the release of fluids from the meat during the first few chews, while the second is the more sustained juiciness that apparently results from the stimulating effect of fat on the production of saliva and the coating of fat that builds up on the tongue, teeth and other parts of the mouth.

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The analysis of variance showed that there was significant difference ($P < 0.001$) in the juiciness of products based on treatment applied (processing methods, storage conditions and storage days).

Table 4 showed juiciness changes as affected by the interaction between processing methods, storage conditions and storage days. The results showed that seasoned smoke-dried product under freezer storage was ranked the highest score (5.000) at 30 days in terms of juiciness. All the products under fridge and freezer storage initially increased in juiciness at the first few days of storage but decreased towards the end of storage periods. The decrease towards the end of storage could be attributed to the decrease in moisture content. Guidera *et al.* (1997) reported that the principal sources of juiciness in meat are the intra muscular lipids and water content.

Table 4: Juiciness: Mean Values of Snail Meat Products (Processing methods, storage days and storage conditions).

Products Storage Conditions	Storage period (days)						
	0	5	10	15	20	25	30
311 Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	4.050 ^b	4.250 ^{ab}	4.450 ^{cde}	4.350 ^{de}	3.450 ^{gh}	3.750 ^c	4.250 ^b
312 Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	4.350 ^{ab}	4.200 ^{ab}	4.650 ^{abcd}	4.850 ^{abc}	4.700 ^{abcd}	4.300 ^b	4.750 ^a
412 Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	2.650 ^{de}	3.150 ^{cd}	3.200 ^{ij}	3.628 ^{gh}	2.950 ^j	3.200 ^d	3.550 ^{cd}
512 Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	4.200 ^{ab}	4.650 ^a	4.850 ^{abc}	4.850 ^{abc}	5.000 ^a	5.000 ^a	5.000 ^a
311 Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	4.050 ^b	4.100 ^b	4.500 ^{bcde}	3.850 ^{fg}	2.450 ^k	-	-
312 Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	4.350 ^{ab}	4.200 ^{ab}	4.650 ^{abcd}	4.250 ^{def}	3.550 ^{gh}	-	-
412 Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	2.650 ^{de}	2.850 ^{cde}	3.200 ^{ij}	3.400 ⁱ	2.900 ^j	-	-
512 Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	4.200 ^{ab}	4.400 ^{ab}	4.950 ^{ab}	4.100 ^{ef}	4.250 ^{def}	-	-
311 Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	4.050 ^b	2.700 ^{cde}	-	-	-	-	-
312 Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	4.350 ^{ab}	3.100 ^{cd}	-	-	-	-	-
412 Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	2.650 ^{de}	2.350 ^e	-	-	-	-	-
512 Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	4.200 ^{ab}	3.200 ^c	-	-	-	-	-
SEM	0.1640		0.1414			0.1787	

Means within storage day bracket having same superscript along the row and down the column are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$).

311= unseasoned fried, 312=seasoned fried, 412=seasoned oven-dried, 512=seasoned smoke-dried

Tenderness

Tenderness of meat can be defined as the sensory manifestation of the structure of meat and the manner in which this structure react to the force applied during biting and the specific senses involved in eating.

Table 5 showed the effect of interaction of processing methods, storage conditions and storage periods on product tenderness. The tenderness of the different refrigerated products increased with increasing storage periods (10-20 days). This implies that there was gradual increase of moisture in the refrigerated products. Iwanegbe *et al.* (2011) reported that loss of moisture contributes to the toughness of meat products.

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Table 5: Tenderness: Mean Values of Snail Meat Products (Processing methods, storage days and storage conditions).

Products	Storage conditions	Storage period(days)						
		0	5	10	15	20	25	30
311	Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	4.250 ^a	4.200 ^a	3.900 ^{efg}	4.350 ^{bcd}	4.350 ^{bcd}	4.050 ^d	4.00 ^{de}
312	Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	4.550 ^a	4.250 ^a	4.450 ^{bc}	4.450 ^{bc}	4.200 ^{bcd}	4.400 ^c	4.000 ^{de}
412	Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	3.400 ^c	3.500 ^c	3.700 ^g	4.000 ^{defg}	3.850 ^{efg}	3.800 ^e	4.050 ^d
512	Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	4.350 ^a	4.400 ^a	4.900 ^a	4.500 ^{ab}	4.900 ^a	4.700 ^b	5.000 ^a
311	Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	4.250 ^a	4.150 ^{ab}	2.550 ⁱ	3.650 ^g	4.350 ^{bcd}	-	-
312	Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	4.550 ^a	4.250 ^a	3.250 ^h	4.100 ^{cdef}	4.200 ^{bcd}	-	-
412	Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	3.400 ^c	3.700 ^{bc}	2.750 ⁱ	3.750 ^{fg}	3.850 ^{efg}	-	-
512	Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	4.350 ^a	4.450 ^a	4.800 ^{ab}	3.850 ^{efg}	4.900 ^a	-	-
311	Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	4.250 ^a	3.650 ^c	-	-	-	-	-
312	Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	4.550 ^a	3.550 ^c	-	-	-	-	-
412	Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	3.400 ^c	3.250 ^c	-	-	-	-	-
512	Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	4.350 ^a	3.400 ^c	-	-	-	-	-
	SEM		0.1686		0.1136		0.1126	

Means within storage day bracket having same superscript along the row and down the column are not significantly different (P>0.05).

311= unseasoned fried, 312=seasoned fried, 412=seasoned oven-dried, 512=seasoned smoke-dried

Overall Acceptability

Table 6 showed that at room storage (0day), there was no significant difference (P>0.05) among unseasoned fried product (4.000), seasoned fried product (4.400) and seasoned smoke-dried product (4.250) in terms of acceptability. Seasoned oven-dried product was the least preferred (2.950) for room storage. A similar trend was also observed at 5days storage at room condition. Before day 10 all the products under room storage were terminated based on obvious spoilage. Products under room temperature lasted for 6days. For all the storage conditions, seasoned smoke-dried product was preferred throughout the storage period. This could be due to the impacted colour and taste by smoke components which had positive influence on the acceptance of the product. The primary purpose of smoking of meat is development of colour and taste. Also, hardwoods are noted for giving off good quality smoke that enhance colour of meat products. Besides, the shelf life of processed meat could be extended by smoke-drying and curing without adverse effect on the quality and overall acceptance of meat (Iwanegbe *et al.*, 2011). In this work charcoal from hardwood was used to generate the smoke. Skewing of the smoked meat could also have added extra value to the product.

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Table 6: Acceptance Mean Values of Snail Meat Products (Processing methods, storage days and storage conditions).

Products	Storage Conditions	Storage period(days)						
		0	5	10	15	20	25	30
311	Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	4.000 ^a	4.350 ^a	4.500 ^{bcd}	4.450 ^{bcd}	3.850 ^{fg}	3.900 ^{cd}	4.150 ^{bc}
312	Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	4.400 ^a	4.100 ^a	4.550 ^{bcd}	4.600 ^{bcd}	4.700 ^{abc}	4.400 ^b	4.750 ^a
412	Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	2.950 ^c	3.200 ^{bc}	3.450 ^{ij}	3.800 ^{ghi}	3.600 ^{ghij}	3.700 ^d	3.750 ^d
512	Freezer(-12.5 ⁰ C)	4.250 ^a	4.500 ^a	5.00 ^a	4.800 ^{ab}	5.000 ^a	5.000 ^a	5.000 ^a
311	Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	4.000 ^a	4.050 ^a	4.500 ^{bcd}	3.950 ^{fg}	2.550 ^l	-	-
312	Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	4.400 ^a	4.300 ^a	4.550 ^{bcd}	4.000 ^{ef}	3.450 ^{ij}	-	-
412	Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	2.950 ^c	3.500 ^b	3.350 ^j	3.550 ^{hij}	2.900 ^k	-	-
512	Fridge(9.5 ⁰ C)	4.250 ^a	4.400 ^a	5.000 ^a	4.300 ^{de}	4.400 ^{cd}	-	-
311	Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	4.000 ^a	3.400 ^{bc}	-	-	-	-	-
312	Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	4.400 ^a	3.350 ^{bc}	-	-	-	-	-
412	Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	2.950 ^c	2.400 ^d	-	-	-	-	-
512	Room(28.5 ⁰ C)	4.250 ^a	3.150 ^{bc}	-	-	-	-	-
SEM		0.1635		0.1159			0.0975	

Means within storage day bracket having same superscript along the row and down the column are not significantly different (P>0.05).

311= unseasoned fried, 312=seasoned fried, 412=seasoned oven-dried, 512=seasoned smoke-dried

CONCLUSION

Colour is one of the most important attributes by which consumers judge the quality of meat and colour deterioration is one of the main factors that limits storage life, at least until the point of purchase. Smoke-dried snail product had the highest mean score for overall acceptability based on colour quality and taste of the meat. The primary purpose of smoking of meat is development of colour and taste. Also, hardwoods are noted for giving off good quality smoke that enhance colour of meat products. The colour of meat products has significant impact on meat consumers' choice besides, one of the major response variables governing food acceptance is colour. The taste volatiles are of utmost importance because they influence the judgment of the consumer even before the food is eaten. Besides, the smoke-dried products had better shelf stability under cold storage than products from other processing methods.

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